

and pycnidia formation were evaluated 21 d after inoculation.

Individual parameters placed all the genotypes in extreme categories. We therefore pooled the parameters and devised a new scale.

Rating	Description
1	0-10% tillers infected; lesion length on first sheath 0-15 mm; no pycnidia formation.
2	10-20% tillers; lesion on first sheath 15-30 mm; lesion length on second sheath <20 mm; 5-10% blotch area having pycnidia.
3	20-30% tillers infected; lesion length on first sheath 30-45 mm; lesion on second sheath 20-30 mm long; 10-25% blotch area covered with pycnidia
4	30-40% tillers infected; first sheath lesion 45-60 mm long; lesion length on second and third sheaths >30 and >20 mm, respectively; 25-50% blotch area studded with pycnidia
5	>40% tillers infected; lesion length on third sheath >20 mm; specks on culm and node; 50% blotch area bearing pycnidia

Using this scale, genotypes were grouped as resistant (ratings 1 and 2), moderate (rating 3), and susceptible (ratings 4 and 5). HAU3800-1, HPU804, and RP2151-33-4 were resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of 26 rice genotypes to sheath blotch inoculation (pooled parameters). Haryana Agricultural University Rice Research Station, Kaul, India.

Reaction	Rice genotypes
Resistant (rating 1-2)	HAU3800-1, HPU804, RP2151-33-4
Moderate (rating 3)	HAU47-3780-33, HAU47-3855-1, IET7641, IET7662, IET7753, IET7758, RP2151-27-1, RP2151-140-1
Susceptible (rating 4-5)	HAU101-60, HAU101-88, HAU3855-1, HAU47-6045-1, IR13420-6-3-3-1, IR17494-32-1-1-3-3, IR19660-181-3-3-3, IR19661-23-3-2-2, IET4141, RP2151-76-1, IET7668, IET7752, RP2151-21-1, HKR101, Palman 579

Resistance of selected breeding lines to green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro (RTV)

V. Narasimhan, K. Saivaraj, and A. A. Kareem, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Adutthurai 612101, India; and C. S. Khush and R. C. Saxena, IRRI

We used artificial inoculation to screen 29 breeding lines for resistance to GLH and RTV.

To screen for GLH resistance, pregerminated seeds were sown in rows in 60 × 40 × 10-cm seedboxes. Seedlings were infested with five 3d-instar nymphs/seedling 7 d after sowing and scored when susceptible check TN1 seedlings died.

To screen for RTV resistance, 10-d-old seedlings were exposed for 1 d to 2 viruliferous GLH adults/seedling (GLH had fed 3 d on RTV-infected TN1 plants). RTV infection was scored 20 d after inoculation.

Resistance to RTV was not necessarily associated with GLH resistance (see table). IR35366-62-1-2-2-3, IR45138-115-1-1-2-2, IR45136-131-2-1-1-3, IR49517-41-1-6-2-3, and IR52280-117-1-1-3 were highly resistant to GLH and RTV. IR41996-163-2-1-2, IR49455-71-3-2-3-2-2, IR50363-8-1-1-3, IR50363-61-1-2-2, and IR50376-80-1-1-2-2 were highly resistant to GLH but susceptible to RTV. IR28239-94-2-3-6-2 and IR41985-111-3-2-2-2 were susceptible to GLH but resistant to RTV. ■

Reactions of selected IR lines to GLH and RTV. Adutthurai, India.

Line	GLH damage score (SES)	RTV ^a (%)
IR28239-94-2-3-6-2	9	10 (3)
IR35366-62-1-2-2-3	3	5 (2)
IR41985-98-3-1-3-2	5	15 (4)
IR41985-111-3-2-2-2	9	25 (5)
IR41993-131-2-3-1	3	35 (6)
IR41996-12-2-2-3	7	45 (7)
IR41996-50-2-1-3	3	25 (5)
IR41996-99-1-5-2	9	40 (6)
IR41996-118-2-1-3	3	45 (7)
IR41996-163-2-1-2	1	60 (7)
IR41999-139-1-1-2-3	1	<i>b b</i>
IR42000-211-1-2-2-3	7	25 (5)
IR42068-22-3-3-1-3	0	<i>b b</i>
IR45138-115-1-1-2-2	0	5 (2)
IR45136-131-2-1-1-3	0	10 (3)
IR47761-27-1-3-6	1	60 (7)
IR49455-71-3-2-3-2-2	1	50 (7)
IR49457-33-1-2-2-2	3	40 (6)
IR49460-54-2-2-2-3	5	35 (6)
IR49492-38-2-2-2	3	45 (7)
IR49517-15-2-2-1-2-2	1	<i>b b</i>
IR49517-23-2-2-3-3	1	<i>b b</i>
IR49517-41-1-6-2-3	1	5 (2)
IR50363-8-1-1-3	1	55 (7)
IR50363-61-1-2-2	1	40 (6)
IR50376-80-1-1-2-2	3	45 (7)
IR50404-57-3-2-3	1	30 (5)
IR51009-62-3-3-3	5	15 (4)
IR52280-117-1-1-3	3	5 (2)
TN1 (susceptible check)	9	90 (9)
TKM9 (susceptible check)	<i>b</i>	85 (9)
ADT36 (susceptible check)	<i>b</i>	85 (9)

^aValues in parentheses = RTV damage rating by the Standard evaluation system for rice (SES) ^bNot tested.

New donors for green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV) resistance

B. N. Singh, D. J. Mackill, R. C. Saxena, and A. K. Chowdhury, IRRI

We grew more than 100 land races selected for RTV tolerance in the field from Bihar, India, on the IRRI experimental farm for seed increase in 1987 wet season. About 30 lines were completely free from visible symptoms of RTV infection.

In 1988, we screened those lines for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens*

(Distant), in free-choice and no-choice tests. During 1989 dry season, six lines found to be GLH-resistant in the no-choice test were evaluated for RTV infection using artificial inoculation in the greenhouse.

Ten seedlings/earthen pot were grown in mylar cages. Viruliferous GLH nymphs fed 2-3 d on rice plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) were released for 24 h on 2-wk-old seedlings for inoculation, at two nymphs per seedling.

Inoculated plants were kept in an insect-proof greenhouse. One month